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D4.3 AI algorithms Security Enhancements V1

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CRISP-DM	Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining
DNN	Deep Neural Network
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
ML	Machine Learning
MSE	Mean Square Error
NN	Neural Network
UI	User Interface
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package
XAI	eXplainable Artificial Intelligence
AI4PP	AI4PublicPolicy

Abstract

Adversarial AI is a menace to the always growing adoption of Artificial Intelligence. With the advent of Machine Learning solutions for the widest variety of problems, some as critical as AI modelling for policy making, it appears crucial to make such solutions robust against adversarial attacks. During the development of an AI model, conditions are carefully controlled to obtain the best possible performance — like starting a seedling in a greenhouse. However, in the real world, where models are ultimately deployed, conditions are rarely perfect, and risks and interested attackers are abundant. Thus, if development is a greenhouse, then deployment is a jungle. We have to prepare AI models to withstand the onslaught. Adversarial machine learning is the study of attacks on machine learning algorithms, and of defences against such attacks to increase a model's ability to resist being fooled. In this work we are focused on figuring out where AI4PublicPolicy models are vulnerable, exposing old and new threats and shoring up machine learning techniques to weather a crisis. Our aim is to create a detector model capable of signalling malicious data from those that are correct as in this way we should be able to create a Trusted AI module that is able to protect the various models from attacks. Since a Detector module will just “detect” but not intervene directly on the robustness of the model, in the deliverable we provide policy makers with another tool, an internal library that holds the state-of-the-art defences and suggests best practices for avoiding adversary attacks, so as to provide tailored solutions to each use case and Policy Maker.

Executive summary

This document (“D4.3 Secure Operations of AI Algorithms and Tools V1”) was developed within the framework WP4 “Transparent and Trusted AI for Policy Management”. WP4 is devoted to producing a set of tools that will make AI solutions transparent and secure.

The main objectives of this WP are:

- Design and implement explainable AI (XAI) techniques to increase the transparency and safety of AI systems in policy making.
- Deliver security solutions to protect against evasion and poisoning attacks that would affect the outcomes of the AI algorithms.
- Facilitate secure and transparent sharing of policy datasets to foster policy sharing between different stakeholders.
- Support policy makers in the use of AI tools through technologies that automate the overall AI-related process.

D4.3 “Secure Operation of AI Algorithms and Tools v1” summarises the work performed in the context of T4.3 for the study and development of Adversarial AI solutions with the goal to ensure the safety of the policies of every team involved.

In this context, the deliverable provides the initial design of the AI Security Toolkit as a function of the policy evaluation layer which aims to protect the policies from Adversarial AI attacks.

The analysed strategies, algorithms and guidelines will be integrated in a web toolkit available for the policy maker to query Adversarial AI Solutions and to use Detector models to prevent Adversarial attacks on their policies.

The deliverable discusses the positioning of the module in the AI for Public Policy platform, as well as the internal architecture of the module along with the state-of-the-art of Adversarial AI solutions.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens' participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project's AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project's developments. AI4PublicPolicy's business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project's platform.

1.2 Description of WP4

Work Package 4 (WP4) is the main AI engine of the AI4PublicPolicy project. The key goal of this WP is to support public administrators through tools to automate the use of AI models, complemented with techniques that both secure and provide explanations on the decisions made by the AI algorithms. It is composed of many tasks which essentially build up the main AI components. WP4 main tasks are the explainable AI (XAI) for the interpretation of policies (T4.1), the main tools / AI algorithms which consist of the policy explainability and interpretation (T4.2), the secure operation of the AI algorithms and tools (T4.3), the secure and transparent sharing of policy data (T4.4) and the automatic ML (AutoML) (T4.5).

The main objectives of WP4 are to:

- Design and implement explainable AI (XAI) techniques to increase the transparency and safety of AI systems in policy making.
- Deliver security solutions to protect against evasion and poisoning attacks that would affect the outcomes of the AI algorithms.
- Facilitate secure and transparent sharing of policy datasets to foster policy sharing between different stakeholders.
- Support policy makers in the use of AI tools through technologies that automate the overall AI-related process.

1.3 Relation to other WPs and tasks

WP3, WP4, WP5 are the core technical work-packages of the project, which focus on three independent and complementary streams of technological work driven by the technical specifications and the AI4PublicPolicy platform architecture provided by WP2.

WP5 integrates the results from WP3 and WP4 with the AI tools, the Open Analytical environment and the citizens-centric optimization and provides to the Pilot tasks of WP6 the interfaces to access resources and interact with the Platform.

Finally, WP5 feeds WP7 with the AI tools and the AI-based policy making artefacts (e.g., AI pipelines and AI models) for the Market Platform and WP8 with useful content to disseminate the AI-based policy making approach. Figure 1 shows all the links between the various packages.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.4 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

This deliverable describes the first version of the Policy Extraction Toolkit component developed in the context of task T4.3 “Secure Operation of AI Algorithms and Tools”.

This component is in charge of providing defence strategies against poisoning and evasion attacks that will attempt to train and use the AI models in ways that compromise their correct operation.

1.5 Structure of the deliverable

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

- The **first chapter** of the document is an introduction to the project and the document.
- The **second chapter** of the document is the background and state-of-the-art.
- The **third chapter** of the document reports the functional requirements.
- The **fourth chapter** of the document presents the solution design.

Finally, the document includes a **fifth and sixth chapter** with respectively the conclusions and the future works.

2 Background and State of the Art

With increases in performance of machine learning (ML), primarily fuelled by deep learning (DL), in modalities such as speech, image, and text, and their practical significance, these techniques are also increasingly employed in critical settings. For example, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are used e.g., to recognise road signs. As ML is employed in an increasing number of systems involved in potentially autonomous decision making, the robustness and security of ML models becomes of concern: autonomous vehicles failing to recognise a STOP sign could result in major incidents, and ML systems thus indirectly also affect safety. In recent years, several methods to successfully attack ML processes were demonstrated.

There are strong indicators that machine learning (ML) models are amenable to attacks that involve modification of input data intending to cause models' target misclassification. The main reason behind such vulnerability is the adaptive nature of ML models. While their vulnerability to attacks can vary, nonetheless, all ML models are generally susceptible to such attacks. For example, an Adversarial AI attack might involve feeding a model false or misleading data while training or adding maliciously prepared data to cause an already trained model to be wrong.

Adversarial AI is a new and growing research branch that presents many complex problems across the fields of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning. The adoption of Artificial Intelligence solutions are growing wider and wider and preventing adversarial learning attacks has become a priority in many industries. Adversarial attacks threaten to undermine the accomplishments of machine learning putting at stakes its further adoption.

Adversarial Attacks are being grouped into four main groups that vary in terms of the goal of the attack or the information that the attackers hold. These four groups are:

Evasion: the attacker aims to avoid detection in order to throw off the classifier and cause the model to misclassify the example. This kind of attacks takes advantage of model's flaws to, for example, elude detections models or to trick classification models

Poisoning: the attacker aims to influence the model at training time by introducing perturbed (poisoned) data into the training set. It has the same goal as Evasion attacks, but it happens during the creation of the model in order to have what has been called a "backdoor" that enables the attacker to create data that will be misclassified by the model at inference time.

Extraction: the attackers aim at reconstructing the data on which the model was trained on. This usually happens in a black box scenario, when the attackers do not have any details on the model's structure and parameters or the data it was trained on.

Inference: the attackers aim at fooling the model by exploiting some vulnerabilities. These types of attacks do not corrupt the model in any way but manage to extract knowledge that was not meant to be shared from the model.

We focused mainly on Poisoning and Evasion attacks because besides being the most occurring attacks (Based on what we observed on "Adversa: Report The Road to Secure and Trusted AI" Adversarial and Poison attacks make more than 87% of the top attacks on AI Systems[15]), after studying the state-of-the-art of Adversarial AI, it was clear that these are the kind of attacks that can be taken care of without having to change the model's architecture or having to train the model over again. Furthermore, in the perspective of reusable policies, not having to change a model's architecture in order to make it robust against attacks is essential for our use case.

2.1 AI tools and libraries

Several papers regarding Adversarial Attacks and Defences are published every month [14], and to go through every one of those papers would be incredibly time consuming. In order to learn about Adversarial AI and its state-of-the-art, it is necessary to find some reliable source of information that condenses years of research and experience. We found some great libraries and tools that can help anyone involved in Adversarial AI to easily get up to speed and ready to implement defence's solutions and strategies. Specifically, we will first use some of the attacks in these libraries to find

possible vulnerabilities in the models created in our platform, then integrate some of the available defence strategies into our AI defence module to protect the AI4PP machine learning pipelines.

2.1.1 Adversarial Robustness Toolbox (ART)

ART [11] is a very important source of information about Adversarial AI is Trusted-AI, a repository that hosts projects in the category of Trusted and Responsible AI. One of the most important project hosted into Trusted AI is the “adversarial-robustness-toolbox” (ART), this library provides tools that enable developers and researchers to evaluate, defend, certify and verify Machine Learning models and applications against the adversarial threats of Evasion, Poisoning, Extraction and Inference. ART supports all the most popular machine learning frameworks and all data types. ART’s repository also hosts a constantly updated collection of papers about AI attacks and AI defences in order to allow researchers to stay up to date on the field.

2.1.2 Mitre Atlas

MITRE ATLAS (Adversarial Threat Landscape for Artificial-Intelligence Systems) [1] is a knowledge base of adversary tactics, techniques, and case studies for machine learning systems based on real-world observations, demonstrations from ML teams and security groups, and the state of the possible from academic research. ATLAS enables researchers to navigate the landscape of threats to machine learning systems. The ATLAS Matrix shows the progression of tactics used in attacks for every ML technique. It can easily be used as a guideline to protect any kind of ML project from Adversarial Attacks.

2.1.3 CleverHans

CleverHans [17] is an important library that provides reference implementation of attacks against ML models to help with benchmarking models against adversarial examples, its name is CleverHans. The CleverHans library is under continual development, to stay up to date on the latest attacks and defences.

2.1.4 Torchattacks

Torchattacks [18] is a PyTorch library that provides adversarial attacks to generate adversarial examples. It contains a PyTorch-like interface and functions that make it easier for PyTorch users to implement adversarial attacks.

2.1.5 Foolbox

Foolbox [19] is a Python library that lets you run adversarial attacks against machine learning models like deep neural networks. It is built on top of EagerPy [20] and works natively with models in Pytorch, TensorFlow, and JAX.

2.2 Adversarial AI Defences

While early work in machine learning has often assumed a closed and trusted environment, attacks against the machine learning process and resulting models have received increased attention in the past years. Adversarial machine learning aims to protect the machine learning pipeline to ensure its safety at training, test and inference time. Defending Machine Learning models involves certifying and verifying model robustness and model hardening with approaches such as pre-processing inputs, augmenting training data with adversarial samples, and leveraging runtime detection methods to flag any inputs that might have been modified by an adversary. There is an increasing number of methods for defending against evasion attacks which can roughly be categorised into:

- *Model hardening* refers to techniques resulting in a new classifier with better robustness properties than the original one with respect to some given metrics.
- *Runtime detection* of adversarial samples by extending the original classifier with a detector in order to check whether a given input is adversarial or not.

Among the model hardening methods, a widely explored approach is to augment the training data of the classifier, e.g., by adversarial examples (so-called adversarial training) or other augmentation methods. Another approach is input data preprocessing, often using non-differentiable or randomised transformation, transformations reducing the dimensionality of the inputs, or transformations aiming to project inputs onto the “true” data manifold. Other model hardening approaches involve special types of regularisations during model training, or modifying elements of the classifier’s architecture.

About Runtime detection Defence we can summarise some ideas of current approaches about it.

- *Adversarial training.* One idea of defending against adversarial examples is to train a better classifier. An intuitive way to build a robust classifier is to include adversarial information in the training process, which we refer to as adversarial training. For example, one may use a mixture of normal and adversarial examples in the training set for data augmentation or mix the adversarial objective with the classification objective as regularizer. Though this idea is promising, it is hard to reason about what attacks to train on and how important the adversarial component should be.
- *Defensive distillation.* Defensive distillation trains the classifier in a certain way such that it is nearly impossible for gradient based attacks to generate adversarial examples directly on the network. Defensive distillation leverages distillation training techniques and hides the gradient between the pre-softmax layer (logits) and softmax outputs. However, it is easy to bypass the defence by adopting one of the three following strategies: (1) choose a more proper loss function (2) calculate gradient directly from pre-softmax layer instead of from post-softmax layer (3) attack an easy-to-attack network first and then transfer to the distilled network. We argue that in a whitebox attack where the attacker knows the parameters of the defence network, it is very difficult to prevent adversaries from generating adversarial examples that defeat the defence.
- *Detecting adversarial examples.* Another idea of defence is to detect adversarial examples with hand-crafted statistical features or separate classification networks. For each attack generating method considered, model detectors construct a deep neural network classifier (detector) to tell whether an input is normal or adversarial. Detectors are usually trained on both normal and adversarial examples. Detectors show good performance when the training and testing attack examples are generated from the same process and the perturbation is large enough, but they don’t generalise well across different attack parameters and attack generation processes.

To give the more appropriate suggestion for every use case and model it is necessary to study the state-of-the-art of adversarial defences. After researching and reading some of the most relevant papers in this field [14] we decided to create a table holding the most promising and effective defences. Unlike other collections of attacks and defences, like the one we can find in ART, this table holds the names of the specific attacks and defences currently used in the state-of-the-art of Adversarial AI. In this table (Table1) each defence is also classified based on the type of attack and the algorithms that might be affected by it. Not every defence on this table has been implemented yet, but they all have some promising research backing them up and we hope to be able to use them as soon as possible.

Even if the number of adversarial attacks is growing and their detection is getting more difficult and computationally expensive, there is an increasing number of techniques to defend Machine Learning’s models against most of them or to mitigate their effects and probability of success.

The countermeasures can be divided into two sub-groups: Proactive defences and Reactive defences.

Table 1. Adversarial AI Defences

STRATEGIES	LOGISTIC REGRESSION	SVM	RANDOM FOREST	NN	TYPE OF DEFENCE
Detector based on Fast Generalized Subset Scan				X	Adversarial Detection
Detection based on spectral signatures		X		X	Adversarial Detection
InvergeGAN				X	Adversarial Detection
AntidoteRT				X	Adversarial Detection
Ensemble Adversarial Training				X	Adversarial Training
Detection based on data provenance	X	X	X	X	Adversarial Detection
Fast Is Better Than Free (FGSM)				X	Adversarial Training
EPIC				X	Adversarial Detection

2.2.1 Proactive Defences

Proactive strategies aim at making the model more robust and resistant to adversarial attacks by changing the way the model is structured or by changing its training process. A robust model might be achieved by different proactive strategies:

Adversarial Training

One of the most successful methods to create a robust model is Adversarial Training. As the name suggests this method implies including correctly labelled adversarial examples into the training set. After training on regular examples and adversarial examples the model should be less vulnerable to adversarial attacks. Nowadays this method can achieve state-of-the-art accuracy on many competitive benchmarks.

Defensive Distillation

Defensive Distillation is a defensive technique that uses knowledge from a different Neural Network. With this method it is possible to share knowledge from a larger and more complex architecture to a smaller model. By providing the model with knowledge from a larger Neural Network we can make a model more robust and capable to nullify adversarial attacks.

Denosing

Denosing is a defensive method that aims at reducing the perturbations in adversarial attacks. This method tends to reduce the success rate of adversarial attacks and it can be conducted in different stages of the model creation. Denosing can be implemented on the input before feeding it to the model or it can be implemented on the features learned by the model.

Feature Squeezing

Feature Squeezing aims at reducing the dimensionality of input space that is usually larger than necessary. An excessive input space can be exploited by attackers so reducing it can lead to a more robust model. This defence implies dropping any unnecessary feature resulting in a reduction of freedom to generate adversarial examples. After feature squeezing the output of the model is compared with the output of the original model without feature squeezing. This process helps identify adversarial examples, the examples that show the most difference between the two outputs are usually the result of some perturbation.

2.2.2 Reactive Defences

Adversarial Detection

There are many different ways to implement Adversarial Detection, one of the most simple ways is to train a small Neural Network to identify regular examples and adversarial examples. There have been observed cases where Adversarial Detection works well even when the attacker is aware of the existence of the Detector.

Input Reconstruction

The process of Input Reconstruction involves the detection and the transformation of adversarial attacks before they get fed into the model, turning those into regular examples. In order to implement Input Reconstruction a type of encoder is needed to transform any adversarial input into a cleaned one. The existence of an encoder makes it very hard for the attacker to create generally effective adversarial examples since without knowing what type of encoder will be used the attacker will be forced to train its adversarial examples on multiple encoders.

2.3 Adversarial AI Attacks

To give the more appropriate suggestion for every use case and model it was necessary to study the state-of-the-art of adversarial attacks. After researching and reading some of the most relevant papers in this field, as we did for the AI defence strategies, we decided to create a table (Table 2) holding the most relevant and effective attacks and classify them based on the type of attack and the algorithms that might be affected by each.

Adversarial Attacks nowadays can be divided into groups based on how they act and on what kind of vulnerability they exploit. These are the most common types of Adversarial Attacks:

Table 2. Adversarial AI Attacks

ATTACKS	LOGISTIC REGRESSION	SVM	RANDOM FOREST	NN	KNN	DECISION TREE	TYPE OF ATTACK
label-flipping (ribaltamento di etichette)	x	x	x		x	x	FLIPPING
R+FGSM				X			FGSM
Feature Collision				X			JSMA
Bullseye Polytope				X			JSMA
Gradient Matching				X			FGSM
Auto Projected Gradient Descent (PGD)				X			FGSM

Carlini & Wagner (C&W) L ₂ and L _∞ attack				X			Universal Attack
M-Attack	X	X	X	X	X	X	Universal Attack
Adversarial Discriminator Ensemble Network (ADE-Net)				X			

Below are brief descriptions of the attacks shown in the table:

Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM)

This type of attack takes advantage of one of the fundamental weaknesses of neural networks: their linear nature. FGSM exploits the linear nature of neural networks by crafting a linear attack (perturbation). This causes the activation to grow linearly with the number of dimensions of the weight vector of the model, making it sufficient to apply many infinitesimal changes in the input to throw the model off. FGSM works the same as Gradient Descent but it aims at maximising the loss in order to utilise the smallest perturbation possible to achieve its goal.

Jacobian-based Saliency Map Attack (JSMA)

This type of attack targets a specific class, in order to do this, it crafts a perturbed object specifically to be misclassified as the targeted class. JSMA are usually white-box attacks, this means that the attacker has full knowledge of the model, its architecture and also of the data used in training. The first step of JSMA attacks is the saliency map, the attackers create one by leveraging the forward derivatives of the model and then use the map to craft an adversarial example that targets one specific class. The saliency map allows the attacker to identify the features that are used to classify each class. Once the features of the target class have been identified the attacker will recreate them in the adversarial example and will minimise the features that are negatively correlated with the target class.

Generative Model Base Method

This type of attack is based on Generative Adversarial Network (GAN). A GAN is a combination of two neural networks: one called Generator and one called Discriminator. The two neural networks of a GAN act in opposition until they reach an equilibrium where the Generator is able to reproduce data from the distribution of the input space of the targeted model. The Discriminator job is to tell if the output of the Generator comes from the input space of the target model or from the Generator itself. GAN are used in adversarial attacks to craft adversarial examples that look more natural than the ones made with FGSM methods.

Universal Attacks

This type of attack aims at creating a single universal perturbation image that can be added to any natural image and causes the misclassification of said image. This single perturbation can even be used on different architectures because they have shown to generalise very well on different state-of-the-art classifiers. The existence of effective Universal Attacks highlights some vulnerabilities that are intrinsic in neural networks. Having highly dimensional decision boundaries, Neural Networks are very susceptible to adversarial examples that lie in the overlapping area of the lower dimension representation of these decision boundaries.

Black-box adversaries

After generating adversarial examples, they can be used in two main forms of attack settings. Black box attacks occur in cases where the malicious actor has no, or limited information about the specifics of the model and how it works.

White-box adversaries

Conversely, the attacker is assumed to possess full or most of the required knowledge about the ML model and its parameters in a white-box setting. Transferability is an especially important feature of adversarial examples. In this context, most adversarial examples can be transferred from one model to another. Consequently, an adversarial example generated and tested by a certain malicious actor can attack other models, either with the same attacker or by others. [13]

Grey-box adversaries

Different from the previous two attacks, Grey-box attacks train a generative model to generate adversarial examples and only assume access to the target model during the training phase. This provides higher time efficiency and easier integration into adversarial defending algorithms. [16]

3 Requirements

The tables given below summarise the functional requirements related to the Secure Operation of AI Algorithms and Tools module. The requirements are enumerated below, while more details are given in the following tables.

Req-01) Identity defence strategies against poisoning attacks

Req-02) Identity defence strategies against evasion attacks

Req-03) Tracking adversarial examples in all the systems of the project

Req-04) Raise alerts for training examples that are suspicious

Req-05) Adopt explainable AI (from Task 4.1) to identify potentially fraudulent data sources

From these requirements we started to organise the work plan and structure the AI Security toolkit. More specifically, Req-01 and Req-02 were addressed in the preliminary research (Chapter 2) we conducted to identify possible attacks against our platform and AI models and the defence strategies that can be adopted to block them. In particular, some of these defence strategies have been selected to be integrated into our toolkit. Req-03 is addressed by design in our component architecture (Chapter 4), as the adversary example detection toolkit is positioned both before the training phase and in the inference phase for all the AI pipelines developed but the AI experts. Req-04 is addressed by a dedicated section in the VPME service that will receive alerts of adversary examples detected by our tool.

We are still working on the integration of explainable AI (Req-05) in the tool. In this deliverable we focused on researching the state-of-the-art strategies that can help policy makers to identify fraudulent sources and how to integrate them in a process adaptable to all the different pilots and use cases that we can have.

Attribute	Description
ID	Req-01
Name	Identity defence strategies against poisoning attacks
Objective	The component should provide defences against attack types that take advantage of the ML model during training.
Priority	High

Attribute	Description
ID	Req-02
Name	Identity defence strategies against evasion attacks
Objective	The component should provide defences against attack type that takes advantage of your ML model during inference.
Priority	High

Attribute	Description
ID	Req-03
Name	Tracking adversarial examples in all the systems of the project

Objective	The component should be able to track all the potential adversarial examples into the whole pipeline of the project's model.
Priority	Medium

Attribute	Description
ID	Req-04
Name	Raise alerts for training examples that are suspicious
Objective	The component should raise alerts when it encounters a suspicious training example in order to allow the user to remove it from the dataset
Priority	High

Attribute	Description
ID	Req-05
Name	Adopt explainable AI (from Task 4.1) to identify potentially fraudulent data sources
Objective	The component should adopt XAI techniques to identify the source of perturbed examples in order to discredit that specific datasource.
Priority	High

4 AI Defence Toolkit

While researching and studying Adversarial AI it appeared clear to us that, in order to implement an effective and useful solution, the AI Defence Toolkit would have to find a way to put in place defensive strategies without interfering with the policy makers and their works. In other words, the AI Defence Toolkit cannot modify the models' architectures or any aspect of their pipelines. Given this we decided to implement a solution that could be easily placed on top of the pipeline of a project and let everything else untouched. In order to do this, we studied Detectors: a family of Defence AI Algorithms able to intercept perturbed examples before those examples reach the model, for training or inference purposes.

Implementing Detectors into the AI Defence Toolkit will allow each policy maker to work freely and to use the toolkit to protect its model from attacks. This solution will also leave room for us to improve and to update the Detectors algorithms with newer and more effective ones when they reveal themselves to be obsolete.

In addition to the Detector, we decided to create a Library that will store information about Adversarial AI Defence strategies, models and best practice. Every policy maker will be able to interact with this library and receive targeted solutions for its use case. The Strategy Defence Library will be kept up to date and will host the state-of-the-art solutions against adversarial attacks.

4.1 Architecture

The AI Security Toolbox will be used by different Data Science's teams working on different models and it will provide tools to identify and block, or clean, adversarial attacks in both training and inference phase. This solution will allow AI experts of the AI4PublicPolicy platform to work on the use cases without restriction and it will also help them prevent adversarial attacks and provide strategies without intervening directly on the model. We decided to structure its architecture in such a way as to give an AI expert the freedom to build his pipeline at his own discretion and intervene later, while retaining the ability to implement some of the best defences to make his model robust against attacks. Figure 2 highlights all the modules present within the architecture

More specifically, we want to use a Detector model to identify eventual adversarial examples during the training or during the inference phase. The Detector will go through the dataset and feed it to the actual model while discarding eventual threats, the same goes for the inference phase: any data will be fed to the actual model through the Detector. It will also be possible to clean the adversarial examples and to use them as regular examples in order to lose as little data as possible.

In addition to the Detector, a Library containing suggestions, models and strategies will be implemented. It will help every policy maker to prevent adversarial attacks. The suggestions given by the library will be based on the phase the model is in, the characteristics of the model and the type of data it will be trained on. After providing that information to the library the team will receive best practice suggestions and the most appropriate defence (or defences) for its use case.

The Library tool will be able to provide the most effective state-of-the-art strategy to make a model robust against adversarial attacks. Suggestion will be provided among state-of-the-art strategies based on the information provided by the Data Scientist about each specific use case. The Library will have at its disposal a Defence AI Table containing all the state-of-the-art strategies to implement AI defences. The Defence AI Table will be updated periodically in order to keep its techniques effective and up to date.

Figure 2. Architecture Defence Strategy

4.1.1 Mapping on the Reference Architecture

The Policy Evaluation and Optimization module is responsible for delivering defence strategies against poisoning and evasion attacks that will attempt to train the AI models in ways that compromise their correct operation.

The AI security model is positioned in the Transparency and Trust Layer and will protect the machine learning pipelines developed in the Policy Extraction module. Moreover, it will integrate techniques that leverage on features of XAI techniques in order to raise alerts for training examples that are suspicious.

The placement of the AI Security module in the Reference Architecture is highlighted in Figure 3. More details on the overall architecture of the AI4PublicPolicy platform are reported in D2.6 “Conceptual model and Reference Architecture”.

Figure 3. Mapping on the reference architecture

4.2 Detectors

Adversarial attacks have potentially disastrous consequences for ML/DL systems. In the physical world, attackers can project well-crafted perturbations onto real-world objects, transforming them into adversarial examples. How to effectively detect adversarial examples has been a challenging task. One idea of defending against adversarial examples is to train a better classifier. An intuitive way to build a robust classifier is to include adversarial information in the training process, which we refer to as adversarial training. For example, one may use a mixture of normal and adversarial examples in the training set for data augmentation or mix the adversarial objective with the classification objective as regularisation. Though this idea is promising, it is hard to reason about what attacks to train on and how important the adversarial component should be.

The detector is a function $d : S \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ that decides whether the input is adversarial. As an example of this approach, a recent work trained a classifier to distinguish between normal and adversarial examples [4]. Based on the approach proposed by Goodfellow et al. (2015), instead of precomputing a dataset of adversarial examples, they compute the adversarial examples on-the-fly for each mini-batch and let the adversary modify each data point with probability 0.5. Note that a dynamic adversary will modify a data point differently every time it encounters the data point since it depends on the detector's gradient and the detector changes over time. They extend this approach to dynamic adversaries by employing a dynamic adversary, whose parameter σ is selected uniformly randomly from $[0, 1]$, for generating the adversarial data points during training. By training the detector in this way, they implicitly train it to resist dynamic adversaries for various values of σ . In principle, this approach bears the risk of oscillation and unlearning for $\sigma > 0$ since both, the detector and adversary, adapt to each other (i.e., there is no fixed data distribution). In practice, however, they found this approach to converge stably without requiring careful tuning of hyperparameters. However, it has the fundamental limitation that it requires the defender to model the attacker, by either acquiring adversarial examples or knowing the process for generating adversarial examples. Therefore, it is unlikely to generalise to other processes for generating adversarial examples. For example, the approach described before, a basic iterative attack based on the L2 norm. Its results showed that if its detector was trained with slightly perturbed adversarial samples, the detector had high false positive rates because it decided many normal examples as adversarial. On the other hand, if the detector was trained with significantly perturbed examples, it would not be able to detect slightly perturbed adversarial examples. During the last few years, researchers have made great efforts to design state-of-the-art adversarial detectors: MagNet, feature squeezing, NIC and DLA.

4.2.1 MagNet

MagNet neither [2] modifies the protected classifier nor requires knowledge of the process for generating adversarial examples. *MagNet* includes one or more separate detector networks and a reformer network. The detector networks learn to differentiate between normal and adversarial examples by approximating the manifold of normal examples. Since they assume no specific process for generating adversarial examples, they generalize well. The reformer network moves adversarial examples towards the manifold of normal examples, which is effective for correctly classifying adversarial examples with small perturbation. Considering the intrinsic difficulties in defending against whitebox attack, it proposes a mechanism to defend against graybox attack. Inspired by the use of randomness in cryptography, this approach uses diversity to strengthen *MagNet*. It shows empirically that *MagNet* is effective against the most advanced state-of-the-art attacks in blackbox and graybox scenarios without sacrificing false positive rate on normal examples.

4.2.2 Feature squeezing

Figure 4. Squeezing Model

The approach, which it is called feature squeezing [3], is driven by the observation that the feature input spaces are often unnecessarily large, and this vast input space provides extensive opportunities for an adversary to construct adversarial examples. The strategy is to reduce the degrees of freedom available to an adversary by “squeezing” out unnecessary input features. The key idea is to compare the model’s prediction on the original sample with its prediction on the sample after squeezing, as depicted in Figure 4.

The model is evaluated on both the original input and the input after being pre-processed by feature squeezers. If the difference between the model’s prediction on a squeezed input and its prediction on the original input exceeds a threshold level, the input is identified to be adversarial. By comparing the difference between predictions with a selected threshold value, our system outputs the correct prediction for legitimate examples and rejects adversarial inputs.

4.2.3 NIC (Neural-network Invariant Checking)

It’s possible to analyse the internals of individual DNN layers under various attacks and summarise that adversarial samples mainly exploit two attack channels: the provenance channel and the activation value distribution channel. The former means that the model is not stable so that small changes of the activation values of neurons in a layer may lead to substantial changes of the set of activated neurons in the next layer, which eventually leads to misclassification. The latter means that while the provenance changes slightly, the activation values of a layer may be substantially different from those in the presence of benign inputs. The method NIC (Neural-network Invariant Checking) [4] extracts two kinds of invariants, the value invariants (VI) to guard the value channel and the provenance invariants (PI) to guard the provenance channel. Due to the uncertain nature of DNNs, neural network invariants are essentially probability distributions denoted by models.

4.2.4 DLA (Dense-Layer Analysis) [5]

This framework is able to detect adversarial attacks during classification without influencing the target model's performance. Inspired by research in neuron-coverage guided testing it shows that dense layers of DNNs carry security-sensitive information. With a secondary DNN it analyses the activation patterns of the dense layers during classification runtime, which enables effective and real-time detection of adversarial examples.

The core idea is: Adversarial examples provoke the dense layer neuron coverage of neural networks to behave in such a distinctive manner that attacks become detectable by observing their activity patterns. Figure 5 shows an overview of the overall process.

Figure 5. Architecture DLA

Hence, it assumes access to the fully trained model as well as (read-only) access to the benign training dataset D_{benign} . We refer to the model that we want to secure as the target model N_{target} . The overall aim is to generate a secure model N_{target}^{secure} that throws an alarm signal whenever an adversarial example is being processed. To achieve this, the first step generates adversarial examples, second extract the dense layer neuron coverage, and third train an alarm model that enables secure operation of our initial target model. The prototype implementation successfully detects adversarial examples in image, natural language, and audio processing. Thereby, it covers a variety of target DNNs, including Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) architectures. In addition, to effectively defend against state-of-the-art attacks, this approach generalises between different sets of adversarial examples. But, during white-box adaptive attacks, this method cannot be easily bypassed.

4.3 AI4PublicPolicy Detector Module

In the previous sub-chapters we have seen some of the main adversarial detector strategies i.e. MagNet [2], feature squeezing [3], NIC [4], DLA [5]. However, these approaches do not always yield satisfactory results. For example, the accuracy of MagNet and feature squeezing needs to be further improved against some specific attacks. NIC has to train a derived model for each layer of the target DNN, which causes expensive computation costs. DLA assumes a specific process for generating adversarial examples, so its accuracy would decrease when new attacks are launched. We observe that the effect of adversarial detection is sensitive to the perturbation level. Specifically, the attacker can escape adversarial detection by adjusting the perturbation level, such as changing the control parameters of adversarial perturbations or replacing a new attack method. Based on the key observation, we divide adversarial detection into two sub-tasks according to the perturbation level, that is, adversarial detection with significant perturbations and slight perturbations. Meng et al. [6] proposed that the autoencoder could learn an approximate manifold of benign examples and the detector based on reconstruction error was effective in detecting significantly perturbed adversarial examples. In another recent study [7], it is revealed that feature filtering contributes significantly to

the detection of slightly perturbed adversarial examples, and the autoencoder is an effective feature-filtering method. These findings inspire us to design an autoencoder based detector that simultaneously detects adversarial examples with both high and low perturbation levels. These concrete limitations motivate us to design an effective and lightweight adversarial detector in an unsupervised manner. How to design a lightweight unsupervised detector is still a challenging problem. In this work we take the idea deriving from a recently published article[8]. We propose an Auto Encoder-based Adversarial Examples (AEAE) detector, that can guard DNN models by detecting adversarial examples with low computation in an unsupervised manner. The AEAE includes only a shallow autoencoder but plays two roles. First, a well-trained autoencoder has learned the manifold of benign examples. This autoencoder can produce a large reconstruction error for adversarial images with large perturbations, so we can detect significantly perturbed adversarial examples based on the reconstruction error. Second, the autoencoder can filter out the small noise and change the DNN's prediction on adversarial examples with small perturbations. It helps to detect slightly perturbed adversarial examples based on the prediction distance. To cover these two cases, we utilise the reconstruction error and prediction distance from benign images to construct a two-tuple feature set and train an adversarial detector using the isolation forest algorithm. We show empirically that the AEAE is unsupervised and inexpensive against the most state-of-the-art attacks.

Figure 6. Complete architecture AI4PublicPolicy Detector Module

Autoencoder

An autoencoder is a type of neural network, which learns a representation for training data and reconstructs the input from this representation. An autoencoder $ae = d \circ e$ consists of an encoder and a decoder. The encoder $e : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_n$ and the decoder $d : \mathbb{H}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, where \mathbb{R}^d is the input space of an image and \mathbb{H}_n is a generally lower-dimensional space of latent representation. We train an autoencoder to minimise the reconstruction error, e.g., mean squared error (MSE). Intuitively, the reconstruction error describes a distance of a given image from the benign example manifold. On the one hand, our autoencoder only learns features of benign examples. When a significantly

perturbed adversarial example is entered into this well-trained autoencoder, it tends to produce a large reconstruction error. On the other hand, the output of the autoencoder is regenerated from latent representation, so the autoencoder could filter out some insignificant feature (noise) of the input, e.g., small adversarial perturbations. It helps us to detect slightly perturbed adversarial examples.

Isolation Forest

It's possible to use a different approach that detects anomalies by isolating instances, without relying on any distance or density measure. To achieve this, our proposed method takes advantage of two quantitative properties of anomalies: i) they are the minority consisting of few instances, and ii) they have attribute-values that are very different from those of normal instances. In other words, anomalies are 'few and different', which make them more susceptible to a mechanism we called Isolation. Isolation can be implemented by any means that separates instances. We opt to use a binary tree structure called isolation tree (iTree), which can be constructed effectively to isolate instances. Because of the susceptibility to isolation, anomalies are more likely to be isolated closer to the root of an iTree; whereas normal points are more likely to be isolated at the deeper end of an iTree. Many techniques were developed to detect anomalies in the data. Isolation Forests (IF) [9], similar to Random Forests, are built based on decision trees. And since there are no predefined labels here, it is an unsupervised model. In an Isolation Forest, randomly sub-sampled data is processed in a tree structure based on randomly selected features. The samples that travel deeper into the tree are less likely to be anomalies as they require more cuts to isolate them. Similarly, the samples which end up in shorter branches indicate anomalies as it was easier for the tree to separate them from other observations. The isolation forest is an algorithm with a low linear time complexity and a small memory requirement [19]. It can be trained with or without anomalies in the training data and provide robust detection results. In our approach, the isolation forest is trained only on a feature set from benign examples and does not require any adversarial examples. It's necessary to test the performance of the AEAE on some specific datasets or images. The results of the study [8] show that the AEAE is more robust against adversarial examples with varying degrees of perturbation than other state-of-the-art detectors. The proposed detector only occupies a small amount of storage space and could efficiently detect adversarial examples. Our initiative is based on all the considerations made so far. It is possible, however, that during the work something may change, or other techniques may be used which are found to be more effective and also more easily maintainable.

4.4 XAI Explainable AI Module

Especially through improvements in methodology, the availability of large databases and increased computational power, today's ML algorithms are able to achieve excellent performance (at times even exceeding the human level) on an increasing number of complex tasks. The user would need access to tons of numbers to explain a Deep Neural Network (DNN), and moreover there is no concrete way to understand the model completely. In addition to the black box nature of a model, bias can creep in when dealing with data. Model performance metrics (e.g., model accuracy) do not always exhibit true prediction decisions. Just having a highly accurate model is not sufficient to trust and deploy the model in real-world applications. Deep learning models are at the forefront of this development. However, due to their nested non-linear structure, these powerful models have been generally considered "black boxes", not providing any information about what exactly makes them arrive at their predictions. Over the last few years, there has been significant progress on Explainable AI. The pursuit of converting these black box models into transparent and interpretable algorithms has gained traction in both the academic and business world. Many articles, publications and open-source contributions have now made it easy to decrypt these complex models and turn them into white boxes especially for business users, managers and domain experts. Today's analytics projects involving productionizing ML models have explainable AI as a key component of delivery to support user requirements for understandability and transparency. Explaining happens at the phase where an ML model is deployed and used in real-life applications. The purpose of this phase is to interpret how predictions on real-world data are made by the model. This would expose human-readable

explanations to end-users, describing how the prediction results are derived – especially important in mission critical applications. Below we present use cases of XAI at the Explaining phase of the ML process.

- **Better decision making.** The ability to understand why AI systems make certain predictions or generate outcomes can help organisations make appropriate decisions. To illustrate, in churn prediction an AI model can accurately predict customers likely to leave in the future, and the business is alerted – however no solution is presented. XAI can shed more light on this decision-making process and answer the “why”. Armed with this knowledge, businesses can formulate an appropriate goal-directed plan.
- **Discrimination.** Datasets often contain inherent discrimination. For example, in 2015, searching for “CEO” on Google Images returned women personalities only 11% of the time. This did not match with the real-world representation of 27%. Unlike black box models, XAI models can present the reasoning behind the result, which can help identify the source for the discrimination and address it accordingly.
- **Justifiability.** As legal questions may not be addressable with black-box models, modern AI systems will have no choice except to add explainability. For example, In the area of individual rights, regulators will demand more explainability from AI models. People who are adversely impacted by an AI system’s decision (e.g. those rejected for a loan) would be interested to know why the system chose not to approve the loan.

There are different approaches for interpreting machine learning models, you can have:

- **White-Box Model Techniques.** Some AI models are simple and self-explanatory. For example, the predicted outcome y can be mathematically expressed as a weighted sum of all of its features x . It is visualised as a straight-line graph, with a as the slope of the line and b as the intercept on the y -axis. A linear model is a white-box model because its mechanism is transparent and simple (as opposed to a black-box whose mechanism is not readily understood). Though simple, these are less capable of representing a larger dataset featuring complex interactions. Therefore, for higher accuracy, we require more complex and expressive models.
- **Black-Box model Techniques.** Black box models such as neural networks or complex ensembles of much lower complexity (like a gradient boosting model based on decision-trees). The architecture of these models is hard to decipher, as it is not clear how important a role any given feature plays in the prediction model or how it interacts with other features. For example, in a fully connected neural network, tracing the output features rendered by a model against a specific causative input feature remains a challenge.

There is another dimension to understanding the interpretability of models. It depends on the model being examined. Model-specific techniques deal with the inner workings of a model to interpret its results. It involves examining the structure of an algorithm, including its intermediate representations. Model agnostic techniques deal with analysing features, their relationship with outputs and the data distribution.

Below we show a brief overview of some packages that can be used to better understand how a specific piece of data has been classified as malicious by the detector model used in the adverse attack recognition module.

- **SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations)** is a game theoretic approach to explain the output of any machine learning model. It connects optimal credit allocation with local explanations using the classic Shapley values from game theory and their related extensions. The contribution of each feature in the dataset to the prediction a model produces is explained by

Shapley values (Figure 7 shows some feature explanation methods). Lundberg and Lee’s SHAP [21] algorithm was originally published in 2017.

Figure 7. Some SHAP explanation features

- LIME.** One of the earliest methods to become well-known in the explainability area was lime. LIME stands for Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations [22]. It helps you explain what machine learning models are learning and why they are predicting in a certain way. LIME currently supports explanations for tabular models, text classifiers, and image classifiers. Knowing why the model makes predictions the way it does is essential for tweaking the algorithm. You should be able to comprehend why the model operates in the manner it does with the aid of LIME’s explanations. There’s a strong probability you made a mistake during the data preparation stage if the model is not acting as planned. Figure 8 shows some examples of variable explanation.

Figure 8. LIME explanation tabular models

- Shapash** is a Python library which aims to make machine learning interpretable and understandable to everyone. Shapash [23] provides several types of visualisations which displays explicit labels that everyone can understand. Data Scientists can more easily understand their models and share their results. End users can understand the decision proposed by a model using a summary of the most influential criteria.” To communicate data stories, insights, and model findings, interactivity and captivating images are essential. The optimum way forward for business and data scientists/analysts to show and engage with AI/ML results is to compile these into a notebook or a web app. Figure 9 shows an example about Feature Contribution Plot made by Shapash. The online app Shapash Library produces an interactive dashboard that is simple to use and collects many visualisations related to SHAP/LIME explainability. It can compute contributions using the SHAP or LIME backend.

Figure 9. Shapash feature contribution

- InterpretML** [24] is an open-source Python package which exposes machine learning interpretability algorithms to practitioners and researchers. InterpretML supports training interpretable models (glassbox), as well as explaining existing ML pipelines (blackbox). InterpretML exposes two types of interpretabilities — glassbox models, which are machine learning models designed for interpretability (ex: linear models, rule lists, generalized additive models), and blackbox explainability techniques for explaining existing systems (ex: Partial Dependence, LIME). The package enables practitioners to easily compare interpretability algorithms by exposing multiple methods under a unified API, and by having a built-in, extensible visualization platform. InterpretML also includes the first implementation of the Explainable Boosting Machine, a powerful, interpretable, glassbox model that can be as accurate as many blackbox models. Figure 10 shows an interactive plot for feature explanation by InterpretML

Local Explanations Interactive Plot built using InterpretML

Figure 10. InterpretML interactive Plot

- ELIS** is a Python library that helps to debug machine learning classifiers and explain their predictions [26]. Currently it supports the following machine learning frameworks: scikit-learn, XGBoost, LightGBM, CatBoost and Keras. There are two main ways to look at a classification or a regression model: (i)inspect model parameters and try to figure out how the model works globally;(ii) inspect an individual prediction of a model, try to figure out why the model makes the decision it makes. Feature explanation in Figure 11.

Actual Target Value : 22.0

y (score 27.362) top features

Contribution?	Feature	Value
+32.107	<BIAS>	1.000
+27.212	RM	6.453
+3.597	B	394.720
+2.547	ZN	55.000
+0.292	RAD	1.000
+0.084	INDUS	2.250
-0.001	CRIM	0.011
-0.174	AGE	31.900
-3.930	TAX	300.000
-3.968	LSTAT	8.230
-6.156	NOX	0.389
-10.159	DIS	7.307
-14.089	PTRATIO	15.300

Local weights generated using ELI5 library

Figure 11. ELIS tabular model

- OmniXAI (short for Omni explainable AI)** [27] a Python library developed and open-sourced by Salesforce recently. It addresses several problems with interpreting judgments produced by machine learning models in practice by providing omni-way explainable AI and interpretable machine learning capabilities. For data scientists, ML researchers, and practitioners that want explanation for a variety of types of data, models, and explanation techniques at various phases of the ML process, OmniXAI aspires to provide a one-stop comprehensive library that makes explainable AI simple. All the modules present in OmniXAI are shown in Figure 12.

Source: <https://github.com/salesforce/OmniXAI>

Figure 12. OmniXAI modules

In our module it is possible to use one or more of these packages: it depends on the type of model we have chosen to use.

4.5 Strategy Defence Library

The Strategy Defence Library is one of the main components of the AI Security Toolbox. Its job is to host state-of-the-art solutions against the most common and effective adversarial attacks. The Strategy Defence Library will not only host the best algorithms used for AI Adversarial Defence, but the suggestions also provided by the library will be of many natures: algorithms, papers, best practices and guidelines. Depending on the Policy, the type of Dataset used, the phase the Pipeline is and the Algorithm used the Library will provide one or more appropriate solutions.

Figure 13. Architecture Defence Alert Library

Reading messages from the VPME Alerts Page, the AI Defense Library Micro-service will be able to extract all the information needed to query the best solutions for each use case. Passing one alert from the VPME as input to the library will return on the VPME Alert Detail Page the appropriate solution (or suggestion) for the policy maker to implement. The solutions retrieval process will be automatized by the Library’s micro-service and the VPME web app that will allow the policy maker to easily access the Library’s information regarding its policy.

This component will be kept up to date based on the always evolving state-of-the-art of the adversarial attacks and defences, once an effective (or promising) defence, or a paper presenting it, will be released, this solution will be valued and, if retained valid, it will be included into the library.

Since the Adversarial AI field is in constant evolution, we came up with a tool that can easily adapt and evolve. After studying the field and reading the most relevant papers it appeared clear to us that a standard and frozen in time solution would have been obsolete in half a year. Updating the Library should keep the effectiveness of this tool constantly at the state-of-the-art, replacing obsolete solutions with new and more effective ones. We also came up with the idea of letting the Library suggest papers, guidelines and best practices for solutions that have not been implemented yet or for project’s phases where it is not required to use a defensive algorithm to protect the model.

In order to receive a response from the Library the policy maker must state which type of algorithms he is working on (i.e. a neural network), what is the goal of the policy (i.e. classification) and at which phase the project is at the moment (i.e. data gathering). Based on the information provided by the policy maker it will be possible to identify the solutions that better suit the use case. All it will take to receive a suggestion is to provide the information stated above and the Library will query the solutions in its archive based on those informations.

4.5.1 Rest API

First of all, it is necessary to define the database on which the information will be based. The DB will most likely be a MySql: below is the schema of the tables involved.

Figure 14. ER Diagram

The tables shown are the following:

Strategy: where there are the various strategies (with their specific name) used against the various types of attacks. The table key consists of the strategy name and whether the model is supervised or not. Furthermore, the reference year of the article in which the technique was used is present.

Algorithm: there are the various types of algorithms used (both neural networks and others) in the field of classification or regression.

StrategyAlgorithm: bridge table to link the information related to the defence strategy with the various algorithms on which this technique is used

Ai Defence Strategies 1.0.11 OAS3

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Figure 15. SWAGGER Rest API

Figure 15 shows the Swagger Rest API in graphical format, created to describe the REST API interface. There are interactions with the STRATEGY and ALGORITHMS tables. For the first we have both a POST/PUT operation to be able to insert/update new records and a GET operation. The GET is used to obtain what might be the best defence list strategy to use in the case of a regression/classification model of any type. At the moment we chose to return an ascending list ordered by published year.

The second POST operation is used to enter all the models (Neural Networks and others) that can be used in the various operations.

5 Conclusions

Taking into consideration all the various types of attack (specifically of the white box type) it was decided to verify the possibility of creating a single Detector model. Thus a sort of layer is created which is independent of the method of pre-processing and processing of the data, just as it could be unrelated to the type of AI algorithm that is used on the data. This specific model, as described above, should be used to detect malicious attacks both in the training and inference phases.

The basic idea in the construction of the Detector is to identify suspicious data by extracting the most important features. Once the features have been extracted, these data are filtered by a subsequent model (a forest) which is able to perform a subdivision into two groups: malicious and correct. This specific Trusted AI module should be callable directly from the pipeline available to the data scientist: once the data manager inserts the Machine Learning module, he will also have the Trusted AI module available. This form could be used in the inference phase to highlight any suspicious data.

Once the incorrect data has been identified, a specific XAI form should highlight the reason why the data in question must be discarded. This AIX module should be integrated with what has already been developed by the T4.2 or created specifically for this type of problem.

6 Future Work

The detector that we are going to develop is especially useful in the search for unstructured malicious data: specifically for images. The idea would be to test this specific detector against various attack methodologies: FGSM, BIM, PGD, and DeepFoolC&W L2. The idea is to use two different image data sets: CIFAR-10 and ImageNet. A percentage of the images will be modified to generate malicious data through the various tools available: for example using the `art.attacks.evasion.FastGradientMethod` class or the `art.attacks.evasion.ProjectiveGradientDescent` class present in the Adversarial Robustness Toolkit it will be possible to perform a FGSM or PGD type.

In any case, the goodness of the Detector model generated also for unstructured data must be verified. In the event that this detector is not usable for tabular data, we will proceed to evaluate the construction of a detector only for this type of data. Therefore, given the need to have a Trusted AI module as generic as possible, it may be necessary to build different detector models or further enhance the one chosen in this phase.

7 References

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